

SOCIAL MEDIA USE AND SOCIALIZATION AMONG UNIVERSITY STUDENTS IN AZAD JAMMU AND KASHMIR

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Abstract

There has been a phenomenal increase in the use of the internet worldwide. Social media use, including the use of Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, and Instagram, has become almost the norm among the new generation. Social media seems to have a significant impact on people's educational, social, cultural, and political lives. People are making use of social media for educational purposes and for sharing information, demonstrating that social media is more than just a tool for fun and entertainment. The purpose of this study was to investigate social media use among university students in Azad Jammu and Kashmir, Pakistan. The population of this study consisted of all BS students who were enrolled in the fall of 2020. A proportionate random sampling technique was used to select the appropriate sample for this study. The sample of the study consisted of 300 students from three public universities in Azad Jammu and Kashmir. Data was obtained through a questionnaire survey and analyzed using appropriate statistical techniques. Findings of this study revealed that university students in Azad Jammu and Kashmir use social media just for academic purposes but rarely for entertainment and socialization. This study has important implications for students, teachers, and the management system of universities. This study recommends that the students make better use of other social media applications, e.g., Skype, Twitter, and Facebook, just for academic purposes. The university faculty may also encourage students about the importance of these social media applications for socialization.

INTRODUCTION

Social media is prevalent in our everyday lives. It has changed the procedures of consuming and presenting media materials including opinions, beliefs, current news and more. Social media use by

the university students, in particular, has been increasing in the last decade (Sutherland et al., 2018). The term "social media" refers to a set of resources and online spaces that are used to meet

people's knowledge and communication needs. It is associated with computer-based technology that allows users, through creating virtual networks, to exchange ideas, thoughts, and knowledge. Students, teachers, and professionals in different fields have been increasingly making personal and academic use of social media (Borgerson and Miller, 2016).

The term "social media" refers to websites and applications that emphasize communication, community-based input, interaction, content sharing, and collaboration. People use social media to stay in touch with friends, family, and members of various communities. Media plays a significant role in our perception of national and international events. For many years, the media utilized different platforms to deliver information, news, opinions, and more. However, the role of media changed when the internet was developed in the 20th century. As a result, the information technology revolution facilitated a technological growth called social networking sites. These networks are often referred to as social media platforms that allow users to connect quickly and easily (Larson and Acheaw, 2016).

Digital media technology plays a major role in this age of modern science, and a person becomes a single individual with his/her virtual identity, posing to conceiving difficulties from the unknowns. In 1972, the first communication medium the telegraph was invented. It was quicker than the rider or the horse at transferring messages over a long distance. Pneumatic post was invented in 1865 to speed up the delivery of letters. In 1890 and 1891, the telephone and the radio were invented, escorting in a new era of remote contact in science. In 1940, the first supercomputer was installed. After that, technology underwent a dramatic transition. Email services were established in 1960, and Usenet users wrote the first interactive newsletter in 1979. By 2006, Facebook and other social media applications had captivated the entire world's attention. Everyday users of social media sites/applications form new relationships and interact with new people. They begin to share their everyday activities on social media with their peers. On social media, their anonymity has been violated and almost every aspect of their lives has become public. They are attempting to be more interactive by forming many virtual

communities. In the fantasy world, they have a different life and culture. Many of these social media sites are all enticing their users by attempting some interesting moves to capture their attention. As a result, people begin to use social media in a compulsive way (Hassan et al., 2019).

Today's internet-based technology is advancing quickly and social media networks are gaining more users every day. Social networking which attracts people of all ages is one of the key indications of this period, as the virtual world extends beyond real life through the applications it provides. Young people, in particular, are very interested in form of media that is an extension of the Internet-based technology. In Pakistan and around the world social media addiction is on the rise. Computers and the internet have become completely integral to human life in this era, which is known as the digital age. Apart from having convenient inexpensive and quick access to the information through computers and the Internet and the growth of the communication network is another factor that encourages people to use social media (Longstreet and Brooks, 2017).

Social media has grown in popularity due to its widespread use and ease of access as well as fact that it is less expensive sometime. Recent studies however, discovered that students used social media to meet new people rather than for education and resource discovery (Akdag et al., 2018).

Individuals use social networking apps for a variety of reasons nowadays, and it has almost become an unavoidable part of existence. People use social media sites/applications to meet a large number of people by sharing of experiences or following what is shared, and this has effects on their media consumption. Many options for exchanging information or communicating through the internet have been made available. Social media has recently been implemented into an educational field and it is helping to improve sharing and collaboration between teachers and their students. When looking at the evolution of the internet between the 1970s and the 1900s, technology and the internet progressed significantly and their use began to affect every aspect of our lives. Because of its widespread use and ease of access, as well as the fact that it is free social media has gained in popularity (Akdag et al., 2018).

The positive aspects of the use of social media are exemplified by facilitating the means of communication. This ease of accessibility promotes student communication with friends and family. Also, the use of social media helps students rapidly share ideas, increases their knowledge, enriches their insights through real-time discussions about various matters and enhances their skills of learning and working with others (Pee and Lee, 2015).

Social media has grown in popularity due to its widespread application and ease of access, as well as the fact that it is free. Recent studies, however, have revealed that students used social media to meet new people and create an imaginary communication environment rather than for education and searching for new resources. With this reality in mind, social media use by the university students was the target investigation of this research. This study was quantitative descriptive study in nature.

Background of the Study

Social Media in Education

Kesici Güler (2019) suggested that in a developing world, education is a critical method. We may simply state that an education is a foundation on which a nation is built. Education can be described as a "systematic method" by which everyone can acquire knowledge and improve their skills over time. It's a valuable commodity that can't be taken away. With the advent of globalization, our educational organization has become increasingly intertwined with information and computer-based technology (ICT). This digital device is extremely beneficial to students, as it allows them to develop at a faster rate by using such technologies. Information Technology is assumed to be beneficial not only to students and their parents but to everyone in every sector.

According to Anderson and Rainie (2010), there are three major variations in how our social lives are structured in Western culture: people no longer belong to set groups that stay the same throughout their lives, people no longer belong to set societies where they can spend the rest of their lives doing the same things, people no longer belong to set groups that stay the same throughout their style of lives, however, we now live in a networked era of individualism, in which the internet and digital technology have changed the way we organize our

professional and recreational activities. Following the internet and the modern world, the advent of mobile phones and related devices as well as improved internet connectivity has resulted in a widespread communication system. One of the effects of these phenomena is the blurring of public and private boundaries. With the social network, internet, and cell phone revolutions all occurring at the same time, understanding is more critical than ever before, how people use social media and how to integrate social media awareness into education. Social networking should be differentiated from similar terms such as Web 2.0 and User-Generated Content. While Web 2.0 refers to the ideological and technological underpinnings of social media and User-Generated Content refers to the phenomenon of people using social media in various ways. In other words, User-Generated Content (UGC) refers to activities in which end-users are increasingly involved in the creation of media content. A community of Internet-based applications that build on the ideological and technical foundations of Web 2.0 and that enable the production and sharing of User-Generated Content.

It is argued that social media can link formal and informal learning through participatory digital cultures. Although there are reports of advanced usage by young people to back this up, the majority of young people appear to be consumers rather than full participants. Social networking has been suggested as a way to address the gap between formal and informal learning, according to academics. It's debatable whether integrating social media into schools has educational benefits. According to a study, incorporating social media into teaching and learning situations can lead to new forms of inquiry, communication, cooperation, and personality function, as well as positive mental, social, and emotional effects. Learning and social networking sites (such as Facebook) have been shown to support interaction, communication, knowledge, and resource sharing, as well as promoting participation and critical thinking, according to research. Positive/good effects on identity expression and digital literacy, particularly among marginalized groups intercultural language learning (Mills and Gay, 2011) and peer support and communication

about course content and evaluation (Majchrzak et al., 2013).

On the other hand, researchers have advised against using social media for educational purposes. According to Kirschner and Karpinski (2010) time spent on Facebook has a negative/bad impact on college grades. Junco (2015) looked at how students multitask on Facebook and discovered that using Facebook while doing schoolwork was linked to a lower overall grade point average. Outside of class, students' use of social media is detrimental to learning, especially among poorer students. Finally, rather than using social media as a formal learning method, students tended to use it for course-related communication or non-academic socializing (Sutherland et al., 2018).

Social Media use by Students

O'Keeffe and Clarke-Pearson (2011) claim that youth use social media to improve communication, social interactions and even technological skills. Facebook and My Space, for example, offer a variety of ways to regularly interact with colleagues, peers, and people who share common interests. In the last five years, the number of preadolescents and teenagers who use such pages has increased significantly. According to a new study, 22 percent of teenagers log on more than 10 times per day to their preferred social networking site, and more than half log on more than once a day. 2 Cell phones are used by 75% of adolescents, with 25% of them being used for social media. Texting is used by 54% of people, and instant messaging is used by 24%. As a result, the Internet and cell phones have a huge effect on the social and emotional development of this generation. Children and adolescents are at risk when navigating and experimenting with social media due to their limited capacity to self-regulate and sensitivity to peer pressure. Cyberbullying, privacy issues, and "sexting," as well as Internet addiction and related sleep deprivation, are all common online manifestations of offline activities including bullying, clique formation, and sexual experimentation, according to recent studies.

Over the last few years, the use of the social media has exploded. It is not only used by working people, but it is also becoming increasingly common among students and members of the education community

(Raut and Patil, 2016). It is no surprise that social media has shaped how people live and communicate, given its widespread adoption. Facebook is one of the most recent examples of networking sites that have gained widespread student acceptance and thus have the potential to act as a powerful platform for students to facilitate their educational communications and relationships with faculty. Students mostly use social media to communicate and exchange thoughts with lecturers in western contexts (Sudha and Kavitha, 2016). According to Hasnain et al. (2015) social media has become a part of our everyday lives as a result of technological advancements and increased internet use). Social media, when used correctly, can help students and youth gain access to information that can help them enhance their academic performance.

Social media has a great influence on student's life. In fact, university students are exposed to social media the most and as a result adopt many new technologies through social media platforms. Academic environments also play a role in this interaction. Most universities require students to utilize the internet and other technological programs used by some instructors within academic classrooms (Alomari, 2019). University students make up the greatest class of social media users compared to any other class in society. However, the purposes for using social media platforms vary according to each individual's needs. Social media has recently been implemented into an educational field, and it is helpful to improve sharing of and collaboration among teachers and their students. Still, it should always be remembered that if the users' purpose and duration of use of the media are out of their control, it may result in negative outcomes (Yang and Tung, 2007).

Key Obstacles of Using Social Media for Information Sharing

The most difficult task that can be encountered while sharing knowledge via online social networking tools is disseminating tacit information (such as expertise, ideas, and thoughts) to organization members. Individual information is intensified and internalized as a result, and becomes part of the knowledge base of an entity. Individuals and organizations can face a variety of main challenges

from this perspective. These factors may include the ability to reuse codified information, knowledge sharing among a diverse range of users who do online activities and the development of interpersonal confidence (Chen and Hung, 2010).

Researchers have observed that managing and exchanging complex information is especially difficult due to a variety of factors, including a perceived lack of personal gain and fear of losing knowledge control. Another issue is the cost and time required for information codification. There has been a decrease in knowledge power in terms of information power. The use of social media for knowledge and information sharing within a company or an organization is driven by a combination of personal or individual efforts to communicate with one another and a desire to assist one another (Alomari, 2019). As a consequence, some of the most significant roadblocks can be related to a person's desire to participate in the relationship, an individual or personal advantages of doing so a lack of confidence and low regard for using social media for information sharing. McClurg (2003) investigated the challenges that knowledge contributors face in an online world. According to the findings, the organizational climate, the essence of information and culture as well as the lack of leadership and the managerial guidance, are all major impediments to establishing and maintaining a vision that promotes online knowledge sharing.

Social Media and Mental Health of Students

Because it has been linked to aspects of mental health, addictive behavior in social media and internet usage is regarded as a troubling phenomenon where other psychopathological conditions can manifest (Alavi et al., 2012). When it comes to researching unhealthy habits, there are a few things to keep in mind; Emotional factors have been shown to raise the risk of mental health problems such as depression, which is linked to anxiety and suicidal ideation, between other things. A variety of addictions, including internet addiction, have been related to depression (Meena et al., 2015). Addictions and suicide are serious health issues that young people, especially students, must deal with. On the one hand, suicide has been related to other psychopathological symptoms including depression

and mental stress, while internet addiction has been linked to aggression, sleep disturbances, and low self-esteem, among other things (Lin et al., 2014). Suicidal ideation is a stage in the suicide process that starts with a thought, intention, or desire for death, progresses to a suicide attempt, and finally ends with suicide. Suicidal ideation is marked by impulsivity, which is also a feature of problematic internet use (Aboujaoude, 2016).

Social Media's Positive and Negative Effects

Positive Impacts

- **Social Media's Impact on Students**

Kesici (2019), argues that, since most students are addicted to social media sites such as Facebook and Twitter, they have easy access to news through these sites. Social media is often used to ridicule other politicians. Students are exposed to people from various backgrounds and walks of life as they use social media. Students benefit from social media in terms of imagination and graphic design. According to the [Student Job](#) blog, Studies have shown that students who use social media more are more creative and have improved memory. It encourages students to be innovative and think beyond the box by opening up new study avenues.

- **Impact of Social Media on Societies**

Man is a social animal who must live in a society to survive. Almost every student, it can also be said uses social networks to communicate with society and share information such as personal information accomplishments interests, or some other activity on such pages. Nearly a quarter of the world's population now uses Facebook. Without social media, social, legal, financial and political ills will go unnoticed. The balance of power changed from the hands of a few to the majority as problems became more evident. If social media activism raises awareness of societal problems, it's unclear if this awareness leads to meaningful change. When people are given choices that relieve them of their obligation to behave, this is a very human reaction. When people may express support in private, they are more likely to show positive support in the form of a financial donation.

Facebook is now used by almost a fifth of the world's population. Approximately 80% of all internet users

in the United States use this forum. Social networks gain popularity over time because they are built on human interaction. Anyone with a minority viewpoint can see that he is not alone thanks to the internet. Before breaking into the mainstream, these individuals would use social media for publications, to create memes, and entire online worlds to advance their cause. Social, legal, technological will go unnoticed if social media is not used. When issues became more apparent, the balance of power shifted from a few to the majority. Social media, on the other hand, is gradually suffocating real activism in favor of slacktivism. If social media activism increases awareness of societal problems, it's unclear if this awareness leads to meaningful change. Some argue that social media has allowed people to express their views on social problems and issues through computers and cell phones without having to participate in physical campaigns. Their participation is limited to clicking the "Like" button and exchanging details. When people are given choices that relieve them of their obligation to behave, this is a very human reaction. Action is required when people are given the option of "liking" a social cause, they use it to stop actively contributing time and money to it, according to a 2013 study by the University of British Columbia's Sauder School of Business. When people can express their support in private, they are more likely to show meaningful support in the form of a financial donation.

- **Impact on E-learning**

The principle of E-learning or freelancing is crucial for successful students. They can gain money by demonstrating their skills in doing online work, and they can learn about their subjects without having to rely on notes or books. The internet age, or time, in which we now live has changed how we use and view things. At the click of a button, everything is at your fingertips, and there is no denying that change is unavoidable. Technological development is the most important transformation humans have ever witnessed. Technology now plays a vital role in education, thanks to the introduction of computers into the classroom and the integration of the Internet into the educational system. This means that the learning environment has shifted for the better, and we must adapt to new technologies and

educational developments as well. Students may learn in a very self-reliant manner with e-learning, choosing their own place, time, and material, as well as the stages of their studies. Students have new and enticing opportunities to express themselves in many ways and openly engage in a variety of dialogues to gain diverse information and cultures through social media. Furthermore, social media networks allow users to connect, engage, and collaborate as creators of the user-generated content, Adding value by using different resources, interfaces, applications, and storage facilities. Individuals with limited technological expertise should use social media applications because they are easy to use, affordable and convenient; anyone with the access to a simple computer can use them. As an educational technology advances, social media has become increasingly integrated into teaching methods. Higher education agencies, for example, have embraced it as a method for promoting professional development education to instill the most up-to-date expertise at any time or place.

Simultaneously, social media has been adopted in higher education as a means of maintaining continuous, unbroken and flawless communication between teachers and students, as well as between students. Despite colleges and schools' extensive use of social media, there is a substantial gap between the young generation's needs, interests, requirements and practices, instructors' attitudes and traditional school equipment. Social media cannot improve education or the system on its own. As a consequence, those who use it whether they are instructors/teachers or students, bear accountability and responsibility. Change, on the other hand, starts with encouragement, eagerness and enthusiasm and social media can provide information that can help people want to change. As a result, learners should be given the freedom to create and maintain a learning environment that facilitates and promotes their learning practices, allows them to engage with their peers and allows them to use social media at any time and in any place.

- **Enhanced learning Opportunities**

O'Keeffe and Clarke-Pearson (2011) described that the students in middle and high school are using social media to collaborate on assignments and

community projects. For example, Facebook and other social media systems enable students to communicate and share ideas about assignments outside of class. Some schools have found blogging to be an effective teaching tool, with the added benefit of reinforcing English, written voice, and creativity skills.

- **Impact of Social Media on the Workplace**

The use of social media in recruiting and hiring has had a significant impact. 19% of hiring managers rely on social media for details when making hiring decisions. 60 percent of companies use social networking sites to study job candidates. For those trying to make a name for themselves in their sector, LinkedIn and other professional social networking sites are important. They give people the ability to create and sell their personal brands.

- **Impact of Social Media on Business**

It is becoming extremely unusual to find a business that doesn't use one or more social media channels to communicate with customers and prospects after the advent of social media. Businesses recognize the value of social media in connecting with customers and generating revenue. Businesses also discovered that using social media to create insights, stimulate request, and create personalized product offerings can be beneficial to them. This is crucial in traditional brick-and-mortar businesses as well as, of course, e-commerce. Integration of social networks in the workplace, according to various sources, would increase knowledge exchange. Project management techniques have changed as a result, and specialized knowledge has been spread. Integrating social technology completely into the workplace removes barriers, dismantles silos, increases accessibility and promotes the creation of more highly qualified and experienced employees. On the other hand, a small number of 'shares' on social networks will result in negative social evidence and jeopardize a company's reputation. Although social networking platforms have become the industry's norm rather than the exception, some businesses have chosen to go against the grain and remove buttons for social sharing from their websites after experiencing some of the negative consequences of social media. Conversions increased by 11.9 percent when Taloon.com, a Finnish e-

commerce retailer, removed sharing buttons from product pages, according to a case study. These findings illustrate the two-edged nature of the social media's effect. When a product receives a large number of shares, it may help to boost sales. Customers, on the other hand, tend to mistrust the product and the business when the opposite is true.

Social media, as conveyed by social networking, is a product of the current journalistic environment. Networks of journalistic functions are formed by online and the social media. Currently, the majority of everyday human interaction necessitates the use of online media and social media. The former is social media, which is a reflection of each individual's and social environment's profile. Several media networks and social media are interconnected as a result of the internet, email, and web-based shortcuts (Conti and Passarella, 2017). Even though the online service community is still reliant on its provider network, users can continue to shape group centers. Journalists may be inspired by social networking to exchange thoughts, events, or other fascinating things relevant to particular networks to link them and use them in their mass communication tasks. Social networking integration in the workplace Users can exchange ideas, chat, communicate and develop relationships through social networking, which is an online tool (Ouiridi et al., 2014). The use of social media in the workplace has grown in recent years (Huang and Liu, 2017). To determine the level of social media use, a comprehensive index was used to quantify the frequency and persistence of individuals' social media usage. It is divided into two sections: how frequently people use social media and their feelings about it (Ellison et al., 2007).

Others claim that allowing workers to use social media at work has a positive impact on their attitudes, actions and productivity. According to Robertson and Kee, (2017), the time workers spend on Facebook connecting with colleagues has a positive effect on work satisfaction The use of social media in the employee voice intervention was successful (Martin et al., 2015), as well as (Holland et al., 2016). Using social media in the work place helpful in increasing creative engagement (Bala et al., 2019). Organizing and displaying job-related resources in the workplace. Employees reported that We Chat groups had a positive impact on their jobs

(Liu et al., 2015). The authors also discovered that sharing personal information in company We Chat groups were connected to a better work-life balance for employees.

According to Song et al. (2019) employees can use both work-related (for example, Ding Talk) and socialization-related (for example, WeChat, Facebook) social networking improved workplace synergies and increased team and employee productivity. According to other studies, employees profit from social media's interaction function in several ways, including improved connectivity with peers and leaders (Liu et al., 2015). Employees' use of social media in the workplace, according to other scholars, has a number of risks and drawbacks. Discussed sharing work-related content in business we Chat groups amplified work-life conflict. Personal use of social media in the workplace would increase techno stress and reduce task success, Time spent on the social networking sites e.g. Facebook, WhatsApp, Twitter, Skype, and LinkedIn, has a negative impact on employee productivity. Excessive use of social networking erodes employees' interpersonal skills and degrades the nature of their relationships with colleagues (Nyland et al., 2007).

According to Rosen et al., (2013), excessive use of social media, may lead to the mental illnesses and other diseases. A study found that social media addiction can lead to emotional exhaustion Sriwilai and Charoensukmongkol (2016), describe the influence of social media on employee attitudes, habits and efficiency has gotten a lot of press, there is no consensus on how effective social media use is in the workplace. Furthermore, although newcomer socialization is a popular usage of social media in the workplace, the literature has ignored the effect of social media use on newcomer socialization.

- **Social Media's Impact on Development and Training**

Job seekers who learn the most recent and sophisticated social media techniques are far more employable. According to a study conducted by Pearson Learning Solutions in 2013, the use of social media in the schoolroom has increased significantly. Over half of the educators polled agreed that social networking facilitates engagement, resulting in a learning-friendly atmosphere. Many educational

institutions already use blogs, wikis, LinkedIn, Twitter, Facebook and podcasts as learning resources. The rise of long-distance online learning has been aided by social media. Despite privacy concerns and some cases of cheating between long-distance learners, social media is still used in education.

Negative Impact of Social Media

- **Lack of Confidence**

It has been discovered that students who use social media platforms excessively are less optimistic or overconfident. They may have excellent writing skills, but they are unable to communicate effectively.

- **Wastage of Time**

Social networking sites are a waste of time. The majority of students use social media sites like Facebook, WhatsApp and Twitter to pass the time. They don't even make an effort to read relevant literature for their studies.

- **Disturbance of Ethics and Values**

Students' ethics and values are deteriorating as a result of their excessive use of social media, which leads them to believe that they have more knowledge and information, they sometimes show rudeness and a hostile attitude toward others.

- **Destroying of Morality**

Social media networks are, to some degree, a source of moral decay. Parents and teachers are not respected by students. They post unethical content on such websites to discredit their opponent.

- **Lack of Privacy**

Social media users are at risk of stalking, identity theft, personal or individual attacks and data misuse. The majority of the time, users is to blame because they post information that should not be made public. Students and others begin to believe strangers very easily and share private conversations that may be misconstrued. This is a very difficult task that social Media is facing. Unfortunately, it is always too late to remove private information, causing people's professional life problems and also their personal life as well.

- **Health Issues**

The use of social networking sites for extended periods of time causes a variety of health problems. Because of constant access to networking sites, it is possible to develop an eye condition. The problem, back pain as a result of sitting in the same position for long periods of time long hours, and so on (Raut & Patil, 2016).

• **Social Media's Impact on Relationships**

One of the negative effects of social media use is that it allows many people to form and treasure fake friendships over true ones. Traditional friendships, in which people truly know each other, want to communicate with each other, share an emotional relationship, and engage face to face on a regular basis, lack the familiarity associated with the phrase friend who are using social media (Enders, 2017).

Methodology

This study employed a correlational research strategy

to examine the relationship between social media usage and socialization among first-semester undergraduate students in 2020 at three public universities in Azad Jammu and Kashmir, Pakistan. The population consisted of 1,500 students from five social science departments, with a sample selected using proportionate random sampling to ensure representativeness. Data were collected via a questionnaire using a five-point Likert scale. Validity was ensured through expert review, and reliability was confirmed with a Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.837, indicating a reliable measurement tool. Data collection, facilitated by personal visits and university authorization, achieved a 100% response rate despite delays due to COVID-19. Descriptive statistics and correlation analysis were performed using SPSS version 16 to analyze the data, providing insights into the studied relationships.

Results and Findings

Table No. 4.1

Use of Social Media Applications

Statement		Facebook	Twitter	Yahoo	YouTube	Others
Which social media application do you use the most?	f	94	43	45	85	53
	%	31.3	14.3	15.0	21.7	17.7

The percentage of AJK university students who used various social media applications is shown in Table 4.1. Thirty-one (31%) of students used Facebook, twenty-one percent (21%) used YouTube, and seventeen percent (17%) used all of the above social media applications, fifteen percent (15%) used Yahoo, and fourteen percent (14%) used Twitter as a social media site. Thus, Facebook was the most popular social media site.

Table No. 4.2

Number of Social Media Sites used by University Students

Statement # 2		One	Two	Three	Four	More
How many social media sites do you use?	F	21	94	83	54	88
	%	7.0	31.3	21.0	18	22.7

The number of online social media sites used by AJK university students is shown in Table 4.2. Thirty-one percent (31%) of students used two social media applications, twenty-two percent (22%) used more than four sites, twenty-one percent (21%) used three social media applications, eighteen percent (18%) used four social media applications and seven percent (7%) used only one social media application

Table No. 4.3

Communities Subscribed by the Students of AJK Universities on Social Media Sites

State	Educational	Entertainment	Informational	E-Business	All
State					

Statement #3	F	40	90	75	51	44
What kind of communities do you subscribe on social media sites?	%	13.3	30.0	25.0	17.0	14

Table 4.3 describes the purpose for which students of AJK universities used social media sites. The kind of community they joined was for entertainment, information, education and above mentioned all type of communities. Thirty percent (30%) of the university students used social media to join communities for entertainment purposes, twenty-five percent (25%) used it to join communities for getting information, seventeen percent (17%) used it to join communities for E-business, fourteen percent (14%) used it to join communities for the above mentioned all purposes and only thirteen percent (13%) students used it to join communities for educational purpose. A large number of groups and communities that were joined by the students were for entertainment purpose.

Table No. 4.4
Purpose of using Social Media site among University Students in AJK

Statement # 4	F	Entertainment	Sports	Current affairs	Educational	All
What kind of information do you seek through online social media sites?	%	50	88	83	47	44
		20.0	22.0	27.7	15.7	14.7

Table 4.4 indicates the information obtained on online social media sites. Twenty-seven percent (27%) of students got information about current affairs, twenty-two percent (22%) got information related to sports, twenty percent (20%) got information related to entertainment, fifteen percent (15%) got information about education and only fourteen percent (14%) of respondents got information about the above mentioned resources.

Table No. 4.5
Students Views about the Different Online Social Media Applications as Beneficial for them

Statement # 5	F	Skype	Twitter	WhatsApp	Facebook	Any other
Which online social media site is most beneficial for your studies?	%	27	44	184	33	32
		9.0	14.7	54.7	11.0	10.7

Table 4.5 shows student’s ideas about various online social media applications that were beneficial to them. Fifty-four percent (54%) considered WhatsApp, fourteen percent (14%) considered Twitter, and eleven percent (11%) considered Facebook as useful application to them. Ten percent considered someone else and only nine percent (9%) considered Skype as a useful social media application for their studies. As a result, a large number of university student used WhatsApp as beneficial for their studies.

Table No. 4.6
The Sum of Time AJK University Students Spent on Social Media in a day

Statement # 6		1 hour	2 hours	3 hour	4 hour	More
How much time do you spend on social media sites in a day?	F	18	82	105	50	47
	%	5.3	27.3	35.0	18.7	15.7

Table 4.6 shows how much time AJK university students spent on social media applications in a day. Thirty-five percent (35%) of university students spent 3 hours on online social media sites, twenty-seven percent (27%) spent 2 hours on social media and eighteen percent (18%) spent 4 hours on social media, fifteen percent spent more than four hours on social media and only five percent (5%) of university students spent 1 hour a day using social media applications. Most of the university students at AJK spent 3 hours a day on online social media applications.

Table No. 4.7
Students use Social Media Sites for Professional Activities

Statement # 7		Always	Frequently	Occasionally	Seldom	Never	Mean
I use social media sites for professional activities (such as jobs search etc.)	f	78	31	48	48	97	3.18
	%	28.0	10.3	15.3	15.0	32.3	

Table 4.7 indicates that, twenty eight percent (28) % of students always used social media applications for the searching of jobs, thirty-two percent (32%) never used social media applications for searching jobs, fifteen percent occasionally and seldom used social media applications for the searching of jobs and only ten percent (10%) students frequently used social media applications for searching jobs. This means that a large number of university students have never used social media applications for searching of jobs. The mean score (3.18) indicates the use of social media sites for professional activities (such as jobs search etc.).

Table No. 4.8
Students use Social Media for Research Work

Statement#8		Always	Frequently	Occasionally	Seldom	Never	Mean
I use online social media sites because it helps me in my research work	f	51	59	38	74	68	3.13
	%	17.0	23.0	12.7	24.7	22.7	

Table 4.8, indicates that, twenty four percent (24%) of AJK university students used social media sites infrequently for their research work while twenty three percent (23%) percent used social media sites frequently for their research work. Twenty two percent (22%) never used social media sites for research work, while seventeen percent (17%) always used social media sites for research work. Only twelve percent (12%) of the respondents used social media sites for research work. This demonstrates that a large number of University students in AJK rarely used social media sites for research work. The mean score (3.13) indicates the use of online social media sites because it helps in research work

Table No. 4.9
Students use Social Media for Sharing Personal Information

Statement # 9		Always	Frequently	Occasionally	Seldom	Never	Mean
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I use social media sites/tools because it shares my personal information with everyone	F	78	53	62	61	46	2.81
	%	26.0	17.7	20.7	20.3	15.3	

Table 4.9, shows that, twenty six percent (26%) of AJK University students always used social media sites to shared personal information with everyone, while twenty percent (20%) of the respondents rarely or infrequently used social media sites to shared personal information with everyone. Seventeen percent (17%) used social media sites frequently to share personal information with everyone. As a result, fifteen percent (15%) never used social media sites to shared personal information with the entire world. This demonstrated that the University students in AJK frequently used social media sites to shared personal information with everyone. The mean score (2.81) indicates the use of social media sites to shares personal information with everyone

Table No. 4.10
Students use Social Media for the Development of the Portfolio

Statement # 10	Always	Frequently	Occasionally	Seldom	Never	Mean
I use social media sites because it helps me build a portfolio for future jobs	f 45	63	77	68	47	3.03
	% 15.0	21.0	25.7	22.7	16.7	

Table 4.10 appears that twenty five percent (25%) of the university students occasionally used social media sites to create a portfolio for future jobs, while twenty two percent (22%) seldom do so. Twenty one percent (21%) frequently used social media sites to build a portfolio for future jobs. Thus sixteen percent (16%) of the respondents never used social media sites to create a portfolio for future jobs and fifteen percent (15%) always used social media sites to create a portfolio for future jobs. This shows that a large number of universities students of AJK occasionally resort social media sites to build a portfolio for jobs. The mean score (3.03) indicates the use of social media sites because it helps in building a portfolio for future jobs

Table No. 4.11
Social Media used by Students for the Development of Skills

Statement # 11	Always	Frequently	Occasionally	Seldom	Never	Mean
I use online social media sites because it promotes reading, listening, writing, and speaking skills	F 54	61	83	40	62	2.98
	% 18.0	20.3	27.7	13.3	20.7	

Table 4.11 indicates that twenty seven percent (27%) of university students occasionally used social media sites to develop reading, listening, writing and speaking skills while twenty percent (20%) of respondents never used social media sites to develop reading, listening, writing and speaking skills. Twenty percent (20%) of respondents used to develop reading, listening, writing and speaking skills. Thus eighteen percent (18%) used social media sites to develop reading, listening, writing and speaking skills always while thirteen percent (13%) seldom used social

media sites to develop reading, listening, writing and speaking skills. This shows that a large number of universities students of AJK occasionally used social media sites to develop reading, listening, writing and speaking skills. The mean score (2.98) indicates the use of social media sites because it promotes reading, listening, writing, and speaking skills

Table No. 4.12
Use of Social Media for Online Learning

Statement # 12	Always	Frequently	Occasionally	Seldom	Never	Mean
I use social media sites to learn online	41	75	74	60	50	3.01
%	13.7	25.0	24.7	20.0	16.7	

Table 4.12 reveals that twenty two percent (25%) of AJK University students used social media sites for online learning regularly, while, twenty four percent (24%) of respondents used social media sites for online learning occasionally. As a result, twenty percent (20%) used social media platforms for online learning only seldom, while sixteen percent (16%) of respondents never used them for online learning. Students who always used social media platforms for online learning were thirteen percent (13%) of the total. This shows that a large number of university students of AJK frequently used social media sites for online learning. The mean score (3.01) indicates the use of social media sites for online learning.

Table No. 4.13
Use of Social Media for Increasing Self-esteem of Students

Statement # 13	Always	Frequently	Occasionally	Seldom	Never	Mean
I use social media sites because these sites increase self-esteem and well-being	43	69	66	60	40	2.95
%	14.3	23.0	29.3	20.0	13.3	

Table 4.13, indicates that, twenty nine percent (29%) of AJK university students used social media sites occasionally and twenty three percent (23) of the respondents frequently used to boost their self-esteem and well-being. Only twenty percent (20%) and fourteen percent (14%) of students used social media sites to boost their self-esteem and well-being, respectively. As a result, thirteen percent (13%) of students never used social media sites to boost their self-esteem and well-being. This demonstrates that a large of university students used social media sites occasionally to boost their self-esteem and well-being. The mean score (2.95) indicates the use of social media sites because these sites increase self-esteem and well-being.

Table No. 4.14
Students use Social Media for Entertainment Purposes

Statement # 14	Always	Frequently	Occasionally	Seldom	Never	Mean
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Statement # 14	Always	Frequently	Occasionally	Seldom	Never	Mean
I use social media to watch movies	55	47	75	66	67	3.08
	% 18.3	15.7	25.0	22.0	19.0	

Table 4.14 shows that twenty five percent (25%) of university students used occasionally while twenty two percent (22%) of respondents used social media sites to watched movies. Only nineteen percent (19%) never used social media sites to watched movies. Thus, eighteen percent (18%) of the university students always and fifteen percent (15%) frequently used social media sites to watched movies. This shows that a large number of university students in AJK occasionally visited social media sites to watched movies. The mean score (3.08) indicates the use of social media sites for watching movies.

Table No. 4.15
Use of Social Media for Updating Individuals

Statement # 15	Always	Frequently	Occasionally	Seldom	Never	Mean
I use social media sites because they are an informative way to update the individual	47	50	101	59	43	3.00
	% 15.7	18.7	33.7	19.7	14.3	

Table 4.15 shows that thirty three percent (33%) of students occasionally considered social media sites as a means of updating individual. Nineteen percent (19%) seldom while eighteen percent (18%) frequently considered social media sites as a means of updating individual. Thus fifteen percent (15%) of the respondents always considered social media sites as a means of updating individual while fourteen percent (14%) refused to accept it. This demonstrated that a large number of university students in AJK considered social media sites as a means of updating themselves on a regular basis. The mean score (3.00) indicates the use of social media sites because these sites are an informative source of updating individuals.

Table No. 4.16
Use of Social Media for Communication

Statement# 16	Always	Frequently	Occasionally	Seldom	Never	Mean
I use online social media to communicate, mobilize and organize national issues like politics	49	52	100	60	39	2.96
	% 16.7	17.3	33.3	20.0	13.0	

Table 4.16 indicates that thirty three percent (33%) of university students occasionally used online social media to coordinate, mobilize, and communicate about national issues such as politics. Thus, twenty percent (20%) of Seldom and seventeen percent (17%) frequently used online social media to communicate, mobilize and organize national issue e.g. politics. Sixteen percent (16%) always used online social media to communicate, mobilize and

organize national issue e.g. politics while thirteen percent (13%) of the respondents never used online social media for communicating, mobilizing and organizing national issue e.g. politics. This demonstrates that a large number of university students in AJK used online social media to communicate, mobilize, and coordinate national issue e.g. politics on a limited basis. The mean score (2.96) indicates the use of social media sites to communicate, mobilize and organize national issues like politics.

Table No. 4.17

Use of Social Media for Private Conversation

Statement# 17	Always	Frequently	Occasionally	Seldom	Never	Mean
I use of online social media sites/tools for private messaging, photo uploading and online profiles	57	34	62	78	71	3.23
%	19.0	11.3	20.7	25.3	23.7	

Table 4.17, indicates that twenty five percent (25%) of university students rarely used online social media sites for private messages, photo uploading, and creating online profiles. Twenty three percent (23%) of the respondents never used online social media sites for private messages, photo uploading or creating online profiles. Twenty percent (20%) used online social media sites occasionally, while nineteen percent (19%) of respondents used them on a regular basis for private messages, photo uploading and creating online profiles. As a result only eleven percent (11%) used online social media sites frequently for private messages, photo uploading, and creating online profiles. According to this table, only twenty five percent (25%) of students used online social media sites for personal messages, uploading photos and creating online profiles. The mean score (3.23) indicates the use of social media sites for private messaging, photo uploading and online profiles.

Table No. 4.18

Utilization of Social Media Sites to Update Profile Information

Statement # 18	Always	Frequently	Occasionally	Seldom	Never	Mean
I use of online social media sites/tools to upload my profile information	59	53	55	65	68	3.10
%	19.7	17.7	18.3	21.7	22.7	

Table 4.18 shows that twenty two percent (22%) of university students never used online social media sites to upload their profile information. 21% seldom uploaded their profile information to online social media sites. Thus nineteen percent (19%) always used social media sites to uploaded profile information, while eighteen percent (18%) occasionally used social media sites to uploaded profile information. In addition, seventeen percent (17%) of students frequently used online social media sites to upload their profile information. From this table, it can be concluded that most of the students did not use online social media sites to upload their profile information. The mean score (3.10) indicates the use of social media sites for uploading profile information.

Table No. 4.19
Group Study Time of the University Students

Statement # 19		0 hour	1 hour	2 hour	3 hour	More
How much time do you spend on group study at university?	f	42	90	96	54	18
	%	14.0	30.0	32.0	18.0	6.0

Table 4.29 indicates that thirty two percent (32%) of university students spent 2 hours in a group study at a university at the university or elsewhere. Take time out thirty percent (30%) of the respondents spent 1 hour and eighteen percent (18%) spent 3 hours in group study at the university or elsewhere. Fourteen percent (14%) spent no time for group study. The survey also found that six percent (6%) of university students spent more than 3 hours in a group study at a university or elsewhere. Only thirty two percent (32%) of the students were those who spent 2 hours in group study at the university or elsewhere. From this table, it can be concluded that most of the students spent 2 hours in group study at university or elsewhere.

Table No. 4.20
The Average Number of Fiend Per- month on Social Media

Statement # 20		Forty	Fifty	Sixty	Seventy	More
On average, how many friends do you make on social media each month?	f	62	94	79	48	17
	%	20.7	31.3	26.3	18.0	5.7

Table 4.20 shows that thirty one percent (31%) of university students made 50 friends on social media each month. Twenty six percent (26%) were made 60 while twenty percent (20%) made 40 friends on social media each month. According to the collected data, eighteen percent (18%) of university students made friendship with 70 people on social media each month. In addition, five percent (5%) of the university students were made more than 70 friends on social media each month. From this table, it can be concluded that most of the students made fifty students by using social media.

Table No. 4.21
Total Number of Friends on all Social Media Accounts

Statement # 21		Forty	Fifty	Sixty	Seventy	More
How many friends/followers/contacts do you have on social media? (Enter the total value of all friends on the social media account)	f	35	82	101	40	42
	%	11.7	27.3	33.7	13.3	14.0

Table 4.21 shows that thirty two percent (33%) of the university students in AJK universities had 60 friends on social media, twenty seven (27%) of students had up to 50 followers on social media. In addition, thirteen percent

(13%) had 70 and eleven percent (11%) had 40 social media friends. Thus fourteen percent (14%) of students had more than the number mentioned in the table on their social media accounts.

Discussions

Results of this study indicated that university students primarily used Facebook as a social media application. According to Asemah and Edegoh (2013), students at Kogi State University primarily used Facebook as a social media application. The finding was also consistent with findings which described the eighty-five percent (85%) of users on Facebook were university students. Possible explanations for this congruence include:

- Maybe they have more friends on Facebook
- This is a less expensive social media application available online.
- They can effectively interact with a large number of friends at once.

According to the finding of the study, university students in Azad Kashmir used WhatsApp as beneficial social media application for their studies. This result is consistent with Church and Deoliveira (2013) and Haq and Chand's (2012) findings, who found that the students primarily used WhatsApp because it is the most common and provides a less expensive means of communication for the students. The following are some potential explanations for the similarities in the results:

- Students used WhatsApp because it is a simple application that is available on cell phones and does not need them to log in repeatedly.
- Students used this social media program because it allows them to call and message their friends and family members, making communication with them simpler and less expensive.

It was also discovered that the university students in Azad Kashmir used two social media applications. The finding was similar to the finding that the majority of the females in universities used two online social media applications, but on the other side, this result contrasts with Ahmad and Qazi's (2011) findings, who found that the majority of university students used only one social media application. The current study's findings were also in contrast to Adam et al. (2012), who suggested that

undergraduates and postgraduates only used one social media application.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Facebook and WhatsApp are the most common and widely used online social media sites/applications by university students in Azad Jammu and Kashmir. Instead of following and joining informational and educational groups on social media, the university students generally use online social media platforms to follow and join entertainment communities.

Furthermore, university students in Azad Kashmir use social media to study current events. The university students spend two hours a day on social media sites and applications. The university students in Azad Kashmir use social media applications for their online learning.

The university students in Azad Kashmir used WhatsApp for academic purposes. They did not consider Skype, Twitter and Facebook as much beneficial for their studies. So, it is recommended that the students may also be encouraged and provided guidance by their university academics to use other social media applications e.g. Skype, Twitter and Facebook to add in their studies. University students in Azad Kashmir used online social media platforms mainly for entertainment. University teachers may play an important role in guiding and encouraging students to use these platforms more for academic purpose.

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